

Asymmetric and Site-Selective [3+2]-Annulations for the Synthesis of High Value Bicyclic Lactams

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Asymmetric and site-selective formal [3+2]-annulations of γ -alkyl- β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes have been developed. These organocatalysed transformations yield high value enantioenriched bicyclic γ -lactams with up to four new stereocenters (sometimes including a quaternary carbon). The overall transformation starts from simple and readily accessible furans and oversees a rapid, controlled and dramatic enhancement in 3D-complexity. Furthermore, a switch in the mechanism operating, dependent on the nitrogen's substitution pattern, adds further diversity to the attainable product profile.

Organocatalysis is a rapidly advancing area yielding many asymmetric transformations useful in synthetic chemistry.¹ It is particularly powerful when combined with tandem reactions because complex enantioenriched polycyclic frameworks can be accessed very rapidly from simple precursors.² The most important challenge for such annulations³ is achieving high degrees of stereoselectivity during the formation of multiple stereogenic centers, especially quaternary carbons.⁴ Successful implementation of these dual focus strategies -addressing both chirality and complexity- can provide very easy and effective access to key targets as we exemplify herein.⁵

Chiral γ -lactams⁶ represent a ubiquitous heterocyclic motif which appears in a wide range of important compounds.⁷ From asymmetric approaches to their synthesis,⁸ the stereoselective transformation of N -protected α,β -unsaturated- γ -lactams is considered to be the most attractive since it is atom economic (especially, compared to the corresponding 2-silyloxypyrroles⁹) and offers opportunities for the regiocontrolled functionalization of each carbon of the γ -lactam backbone.¹⁰ However, there is limited substrate flexibility for the lactam precursors. For instance, the γ -alkyl-substituted and the N -unprotected counterparts have never been utilized. Herein, we introduce a regio-, diastereo- and enantioselective functionalization of γ -alkyl- β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams utilizing α,β -unsaturated aldehydes as electrophiles and catalytic diphenylprolinol silyl ether (cat. **I**, Scheme 1),¹¹ as a highly effective means for accessing these privileged compounds; including, even those with an enantioenriched quaternary center at the lactam's γ -position.

β,γ -Unsaturated- γ -lactams of type **2** or **3** (Scheme 1) were easily prepared by a protocol beginning with the photooxygenation (singlet oxygen) of simple furans of type **1**.¹² We envisioned that the resultant lactams¹³ might serve as versatile reaction partners via controlled reaction at any one of their multiple nucleophilic positions. It was hoped that they might be partnered with dielectrophilic α,β -unsaturated aldehydes activated through iminium-ion catalysis.¹⁴ To the best of our knowledge there is no precedent for these formal [3+2] annulations introduced in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Selective formal [3+2]-annulations of β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams.

To initiate the investigation, we synthesized 2-pyrrolidinone **2a** using the singlet oxygen mediated transformation of furan **1a** (Scheme 2, **1**→**2**).^{12,13} Purified **2a** was then subjected to various conditions using LUMO-lowering catalysts **I** - **III** (cat. **I** - **III**) and cinnamaldehyde (**4a**). Strikingly, cat. **I** promoted the formation of bicyclic lactam **5aa**, bearing three newly-

Scheme 2. Asymmetric [3+2]-annulations of β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams **2 with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes **4**.**

^aAll the reactions were performed using 0.2 mmol of **2**. ^bDetermined by crude ¹H NMR spectrum. ^cDetermined by chiral HPLC analysis of the major diastereoisomer. ^dIsolated yield for major diastereoisomer.

formed stereocenters, via vinylogous Michael-addition¹⁵ followed by hemi-aminalization (Scheme 2). We found that the optimal conditions were conditions A (15 mol % of cat. **I** at 0 °C to rt, 18 h) in DCE using 1.5 equiv of **4a** (90% de, 98% ee, 68% yield for the major diastereoisomer). At room temperature, the same reaction (10% of cat. **I** in DCM, DCE or toluene) was completed within 12 h albeit with lower de values (see, cond. B and C). Amongst the other conditions that were tested, cat. **II** and **III** (cond. D) proved ineffective and other solvents such as MeOH, CH₃CN or CH₃CN/H₂O (cond. E-G) had reactivity or stereoselectivity issues. Furthermore, the presence of benzoic acid (cond. H) significantly diminished the diastereoselectivity. This result, as well as, the outcome of the reactions undertaken in MeOH and CH₃CN/H₂O, played a substantive role in the mechanistic rationale that is presented. We propose that the stereoselectivity results from an ion-pair transition state (TS_{1-endo}, TS_{2-exo} is disfavoured due to the steric hindrance between the -CH₂R¹ and -R² groups) that forces the *Si* face of the γ -lactam to react from the *Si* face of the iminium ion in the first stage of the transformation (**2** + **4** → **5i**, Scheme 2).¹⁶ This transition state could easily be disrupted by the presence of an acid or a protic solvent (*vide infra*). The aldehyde group in **5ii** is subsequently trapped from the *Si* face to form hemiaminal **5** (H-bond directed cyclization). Intermediate **5ii** can also be reduced to the corresponding alcohol of

type **7**. The formation of an enantioenriched quaternary center at the γ -position of the lactams is highly desirable for the synthesis of alkaloids bearing α -tertiary amines.¹⁷ Furthermore, compounds of type **5** constitute key building blocks for the common pyrrolizidine alkaloids.¹⁸

To explore the scope of the reaction, different α,β -unsaturated aldehydes **4** and 2-pyrrolidinones **2** were tested under conditions A (Scheme 2). In most cases, the reactions proceeded with excellent diastereo- and enantioselectivity and with good isolated yields for the major diastereoisomer. Amongst the aldehydes that were used, **4d** proved to be less reactive under conditions A, since its reaction with **2a** did not reach completion after 18 h (conv 60%, 30% yield). However, when the same substrates were subjected to conditions B (in DCE) consumption of **2a** within 12 h affording **5ad** was observed (Scheme 2). An adjustment in the conditions was also needed for the alkyl chain-bearing aldehyde **4e** (2.5 equiv of **4e**, 20% cat. **I**, 0 °C to rt) to achieve complete consumption of the starting 2-pyrrolidinones **2a** and **2c** within 48 h [see Supporting Information (SI)]. The resulting compounds, **5ae** and **5ce**, were delivered with excellent diastereo- and enantioselectivity albeit in slightly lower yields. For many of the aforementioned cases, the reaction was terminated at the final stage of the process by adding NaBH₄ leading to enantiopure compounds **7** (Scheme 2). The

Scheme 3. Asymmetric [3+2]-annulations of β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams **3 with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes **4**.**

^aAll the reactions were performed using 0.2 mmol of **3**, or **1** (in case of cond. Q). ^bDetermined by crude ¹H NMR spectrum. ^cDetermined by chiral HPLC analysis of the major diastereoisomer. ^dIsolated yield for the major diastereoisomer.

de of **7** remains unchanged when compared with the precursor compounds **5** meaning that the hemiaminal stereocenter is not responsible for the observed diastereoselectivity.

An interesting observation emerged via the reaction of 2-pyrrolidinone **2d** with aldehyde **4a**. Even though the [3+2]-annulation proceeded as expected and the crude NMR spectrum revealed the formation of product **5da** with 88% de, this de value was significantly reduced to 66% during the chromatographic purification of the product.¹⁹ Similar de values were measured after reduction of **5da** with NaBH₄ (for product **7da**: 88% de when **5da** was not isolated and 66% de when starting from purified **5da**). This result is a consequence of the reversibility of the reaction under chromatography conditions. For further examination of the reaction, the minor stereoisomer **5da'** was synthesized and characterized. Specifically, the reaction of **2d** with **4a** under conditions E or H favored this diastereomer, while conditions I at 50 °C significantly shifted the de towards **5da'** (60% de, Scheme 2). In addition, isomerization (**5da**→**5da'**) was observed when purified **5da** was subjected to the same conditions. These observations not only support the contention that the reaction is reversible, but also lend credence to the mechanistic proposal, meaning that any factor that intervenes at the TS₁ (e.g. protic solvent or PhCO₂H) leads to diminished de values (*vide supra*).

The relative configuration of compounds of type **5**, and, consequently, for compounds **7**, was determined via NOE studies for representative compounds of type **5**. The absolute configuration of the major diastereoisomer was determined via the derivatization of compound **5cb** into the corresponding *R*- and *S*-MTPA esters (Mosher ester analysis).²⁰

Our efforts turned next to examining the influence of the *N*-substituent of the starting lactam. *N*-benzyl-2-pyrrolidinone **3a** was synthesized using the singlet oxygen

based protocol,^{12,13} and, subsequently, treated with 1.5 equiv of cinnamaldehyde (**4a**) and 10% of cat. **I** in DCE (cond. I, Scheme 3). No reaction was observed after 24 h at rt. To our delight, however, addition of benzoic acid (10 mol %) dramatically shifted the reaction towards compound **6aa** bearing four newly-formed stereogenic centers and a *E*-configured double bond (cond. J, 30% de, 88% ee, the minor diastereoisomer was **6aa'**). In this case, the product was derived by a Michael-addition of lactam **3a** from its α -position to the LUMO-activated aldehyde **4a** (**3** + **4** → **6i**) followed by the trapping of the aldehyde group by the enamide double bond (**6ii**→**6**, Scheme 3). Bicycles of type **6** also constitute building block for naturally occurring alkaloids.²¹ Various conditions were tested in order to optimize this second annulation process. Toluene was found to be a better solvent for the reaction (on going from cond. K to L, the de increased). In addition, decreasing the amount of PhCO₂H from 10% (cond. L) to just 5% (cond. M) further increased the de value. Reduction of the temperature led to improvements in the yield, diastereo- and enantioselectivity (cond. N, 62%, 70% de and 97% ee). Other catalysts or solvents did not effectively promote the reaction (cond. O and P). Most interestingly, performing the reaction as a one-pot process from furan **1a** (without purification of **3a**), the final product **6aa** was obtained in good overall isolated yield (60% for the major diastereoisomer) and with very good stereoselectivities (cond. Q, 82% de and 98% ee).²² By completing this transformation, a very rapid increase in molecular complexity starting from a simple precursor (furan **1**) had been achieved in one synthetic operation. After establishing the optimized conditions (cond. Q), various furan substrates and aldehydes were tested for the preparation of different enantiopure bicycles of type **6**. The results are reported in Scheme 3. The overall isolated yields are very good considering that five contiguous reactions are included in this one pot process.

The relative configuration, as well as, the geometrical configuration of the compounds of type **6** was elucidated via NOE studies of some representative compounds.²⁰ The absolute configuration was determined via the derivatization of compounds **6aa** and **6aa'** into the corresponding *R*- and *S*-MTPA esters,²⁰ and, was unambiguously, confirmed via single-crystal X-ray analysis of product **6dd**.²³

We propose that this reaction proceeds through an ion-dipole transition state (TS-*endo*, Scheme 3) which defines the diastereo and enantioselectivities (the *Si* face of the 2-pyrrolidinone reacts with the *Si* face of the iminium ion). This type of interaction is weaker compared to the ion-pair transition state proposed for the synthesis of bicycles **5** (Scheme 2); thus, explaining the small reduction in the *d_e* values (up to 84% compared with up to 99% for **5**). It is notable that the TS-*endo* here differs from the TS₂-*exo* described in Scheme 2, because the nucleophile **3** is at the right position for α -attack, and, thus, avoids the unfavorable R¹/R² interaction. Furthermore, the R¹ groups are forced by the benzyl group into an anti conformation which explains the *E*-configured double bond in the final product. Since the vinylogous Michael-addition (**2**→**5i**, Scheme 2) is reversible and the presence of the *N*-benzyl group is blocking the formation of lactam of type **5** (**5ii**→**5** is blocked), the reaction proceeds reversibly to intermediate **6i**. Benzoic acid may be responsible for accelerating a hydrogen-bond directed cyclization (**6ii**→**6**) in which the aldehyde is attacked on its *Si* face; thus, establishing the stereochemistry of the final two stereocenters.

In summary, we have disclosed novel asymmetric formal [3+2]-annulations of γ -alkyl- β,γ -unsaturated- γ -lactams (readily prepared by photooxygenation of simple furans) with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes catalyzed by an organocatalyst. These site-selective cyclizations afford high value chiral bicyclic γ -lactams bearing up to four stereocenters with significant levels of diastereo- and enantioselectivity.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. Detailed experimental procedures, spectral data, and analytical data (PDF).

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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(19) This alteration in diastereomeric ratio was also observed with other products of type **5**; however, at significantly lower levels than that seen for **5da**.

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(23) CCDC 1586973 contains the supplementary crystallographic data. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.